

Laser Interferometer Lunar Antenna (LILA): The Gravitational-Wave and Lunar Science next frontier K. Jani¹, P. Lognonné² on behalf of the LILA Consortium, ¹Vanderbilt University, Vanderbilt Lunar Labs Initiative and Department of Physics and Astronomy, Nashville, TN 37235, USA, Karan.jani@vanderbilt.edu, ²Université Paris Cité, Institut de physique du globe de Paris, France, lognonne@ipgp.fr

Introduction: The Laser Interferometer Lunar Antenna (LILA) is a next-generation gravitational-wave (GW) facility on the Moon [1,2]. By harnessing the Moon’s unique environment, LILA fills a critical observational gap in the mid-band GW spectrum (0.1 – 10 Hz) between terrestrial detector LIGO and the future space mission LISA. Observations enabled by LILA will fundamentally transform multi-messenger astrophysics and GW probes of fundamental physics. LILA will measure the lunar deep interior better than any existing planetary seismic instruments. The LILA mission is designed for phased development aligned with capabilities of the CLPS and Artemis programs. LILA is a unique collaboration between universities, space industries and international partners.

Science Goals: The LILA mission supports the top priorities in Pathways to Discovery in Astronomy and Astrophysics for the 2020s (New Windows on the Dynamic Universe, Unveiling the Drivers of Galaxy Growth), Origins, Planetary Science, and Astrobiology Decadal 2023- 2032 (Deep Interior Lunar Geophysics), and Biological and Physical Sciences Decadal 2023-2032 (Search for New Physics), and its development is aligned with NASA’s Moon-to-Mars Objective: “Advance understanding of physical systems and fundamental physics by utilizing the unique environments of the Moon.” Observations enabled by LILA will advance astronomy, fundamental physics, and lunar science.

Phase Implementation for LILA Mission: Based on Apollo data, studies have shown that Moon’s low seismic noise opens the mid-band GW spectrum. The surface lacks atmospheric disturbances (wind, pressure variations, humidity) and lacks anthropogenic or acoustic noise sources. The natural vacuum surpasses LIGO’s ultra-high vacuum. Therefore, building LILA requires no major lunar infrastructure. Unlike space missions like LISA that have a limited lifetime due to orbital pull, LILA will operate for a decade or longer. The deployment of LILA is structured into two phases:

LILA-Pioneer (near term): A baseline interferometer (3 to 5 km) deployed with the current generation of CLPS lander. The primary payload hosts the optical setup, seismometer, camera, and on-board computing, all inside a dust-protected, thermally managed case atop scaffolding. The secondary payloads consists of a retroreflector and seismic monitor.

LILA-Horizon (long term): A 40-km three-station interferometer requiring larger cargo capacity and expansive surface mobility. Each station hosts a seismic isolation system and a quantum-enhanced laser frequency comb sensor, GravComb. LILA-Horizon delivers two transformative science returns: (i) millihertz to kilo-hertz broadband GW sensitivity, enabling multi-band, multi-messenger astrophysics from a single lunar site; (ii) massive improvement in mid-band GW sensitivity over LILA-Pioneer, enabling detection to the cosmic horizon.

Site-Agnostic Deployment and Location Requirements: LILA is viable on any lunar site; however, optimal scientific returns and minimal engineering complexity require: (1) End stations have to be placed at few ~meters elevation from primary station for LILA-Pioneer (~km for LILA-Horizon) for an unobstructed line of sight. (2) Must conform to LTV’s range and terrain constraints for deployment. (3) Shallow moonquakes may occur near lunar scarps, which should be avoided. (4) Dust, radiation, and thermal factors favor non-equatorial sites (5) Regions near other human activities (such as Artemis Base Camp) should be avoided (6) LILA-Horizon should be established near LILA-Pioneer to ensure characterization of lunar environment on GW sensitivity.

Role of Human Presence: Although LILA is designed for autonomous operations, the presence of astronauts will be critical for: (1) Modular Assembly and alignment (2) Minimal “hands-on” maintenance will be needed (~every five years) for occasional dust cleaning from optics or actuators, re-coating baffles, and manual retuning after modular replacements. Astronauts, guided by on-Earth specialists, can perform upgrades for LILA-Horizon.

References: [1] K. Jani and A. Loeb (2021), *JCAP06*, 044. [2] K. Jani et al. (2025) submitted to NASEM study on key non-polar destinations for decadal-level science.